

The Influence of Competencies, Remuneration, Information Technology Facilities and Career Development on Lecturer Work Ethic and Its Implications on Lecturer Performance

Pujiono¹, Azhar Affandi², Heru Setiawan²

¹Bandung Health Polytechnic, Pajajaran St. No.56, Bandung, Indonesia.

²Doctoral Program in Management Science, Pasundan University, Sumatera St. No.41, Bandung, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT: Higher education in Indonesia plays a role in enlightening the nation and improving welfare through the development of knowledge and the Tridharma of Higher Education. Lecturers, as professional educators, play a crucial role in the transformation and dissemination of knowledge. Therefore, improving the quality of lecturers and good educational governance are key factors in ensuring the quality of higher education. This study aims to analyze the factors influencing lecturers' work ethic on their performance, through the variables of competence, remuneration, information technology facilities, and career development. The study employs a descriptive method and a quantitative verificative method with a cross-sectional design. The population consists of 483 lecturers, with a filtered sample of 220 lecturers from Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y. Questionnaires were distributed to these participants, followed by validity, reliability, and normality tests. Data analysis includes descriptive analysis with score ranges, and verificative analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with Lisrel 8.8 to accommodate latent variables and address measurement errors. Model feasibility testing was conducted using various goodness-of-fit indicators. The results indicate that the variables of competence, remuneration, technology facilities, and career development for lecturers at Poltekkes X and Y fall into the fairly good and good category, while work ethic significantly influences lecturer performance. However, improvements are needed, particularly in professionalism, remuneration, satisfaction with information technology facilities, as well as policies on transfers and promotions. Additionally, in terms of work ethic, the reliability aspect needs improvement to enhance lecturer performance.

KEYWORDS: Competence; Remuneration; Information Technology Facilities; Career Development; Work Ethic; Lecturer Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Higher education in Indonesia plays a strategic role in advancing national intellectual capacity and improving societal welfare, as mandated by the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia (Indonesia, 2002). Within the context of national development, higher education also contributes to the advancement of science and technology while preserving cultural values, democracy, and tolerance (Nurwardani et al., 2016). The planning and governance of higher education must therefore be carried out systematically and sustainably in order to address global challenges and enhance national competitiveness (Akhmaloka et al., 2023).

Higher education in Indonesia is regulated under Law No. 3 of 2020, which encompasses a range of academic levels from diploma to doctoral programs, as well as professional and specialist programs (Indonesia, 2020a). Universities and higher education institutions are entrusted with implementing the Tridharma Perguruan Tinggi (Three Pillars of Higher Education), namely education, research, and community service. Faculty members, as professional educators, play a pivotal role in the transformation and dissemination of knowledge. Thus, improving faculty quality and establishing good governance are key determinants in ensuring the quality of higher education (Indonesia, 2005).

As part of the higher education system, Health Polytechnics (Politeknik Kesehatan or Poltekkes) are mandated to provide vocational and professional education in the health sector. According to the Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No. 71 of 2020, Poltekkes carry out the Tridharma Perguruan Tinggi with an emphasis on practice-based education to produce competent health professionals (Indonesia, 2020b). In this regard, Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y have adopted the Public Service Agency (Badan Layanan Umum—BLU) model, which provides financial management flexibility to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of educational services (Indonesia, 2020c).

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The contribution of higher education to human development can be measured through the Human Development Index (HDI), which serves as a key indicator of societal welfare at the regional and national levels (Sobarna, 2006). The HDI, developed by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in 1990, comprises three core dimensions: health (life expectancy), education (literacy and school participation), and standard of living (income per capita) (United Nations Development Programme [UNDP], 2019). It is widely used as a comparative measure of welfare across regions and as a foundation for designing socio-economic development policies.

In Indonesia, the HDI has shown consistent improvement. In 2022, the HDI of West Java Province reached 73.12, with an average annual growth rate of 0.84% over the past 12 years (Statistics Indonesia [BPS] West Java Province, 2022). Cities such as Bandung, Bekasi, and Depok recorded HDI values above 80, placing them in the category of very high human development. Meanwhile, the HDI of Central Java Province increased to 72.79 in 2022, with Salatiga City achieving the highest HDI at 84.35. These upward trends highlight the vital role of education in supporting human capital development and societal well-being (Sobarna, 2006).

As health education institutions, Poltekkes contribute directly to HDI improvement by producing qualified health professionals. The availability of competent health personnel positively influences life expectancy and the quality of healthcare services, both of which are central components of HDI measurement. Furthermore, access to quality vocational health education enables individuals to acquire professional skills that enhance their standard of living. Accordingly, the roles of Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y in developing human resources in the health sector are crucial for achieving sustainable human development.

Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y were selected as the focus of this study because they are classified as Class I Poltekkes in Indonesia, with substantial human resources and state-owned assets. Their strong institutional performance positions them as models in advancing the quality of health education and research. This study therefore aims to analyze the factors influencing faculty work ethic, including competence, remuneration, information technology facilities, and career development. In addition, given that these institutions operate under the BLU management system of the Ministry of Health, the effectiveness and efficiency of BLU implementation are also examined to ensure optimal management in enhancing the quality of education and health services.

Preliminary observations indicate several challenges in human resource management at Poltekkes, such as gaps in faculty competence mapping, suboptimal performance, and remuneration schemes that remain insufficiently competitive. Moreover, limitations in information technology infrastructure and career development opportunities continue to hinder efforts to improve faculty quality. Hence, this study seeks to identify and analyze these factors and assess their influence on the work ethic and performance of faculty members at both Poltekkes.

The findings of this research are expected to provide strategic recommendations for improving faculty quality and strengthening the effectiveness of health polytechnic education systems at Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y. Enhancing faculty performance is anticipated to contribute to better graduate outcomes, which in turn will support improvements in the HDI and the overall welfare of society.

METHODS

This study employed descriptive and verificative methods. The descriptive method was used to systematically illustrate research variables without linking them to others (Sugiyono, 2018). The verificative method examined the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable and tested the proposed hypotheses. The research applied a quantitative design with a cross-sectional approach, where data were collected directly from respondents to provide an empirical overview of the variables (Creswell & Creswell, 2022).

The population consisted of 483 faculty members from Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y. The sample was determined through stratified proportional random sampling, using the Slovin formula, resulting in 220 respondents (Santoso, 2023). Data collection was conducted via a structured questionnaire that had been tested for validity and reliability. Validity testing ensured that the instrument measured the intended constructs, using Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Loading Factor values (Hair et al., 2014). An instrument was considered valid when $AVE > 0.50$ and factor loading > 0.50 (Imam Ghazali, 2021). Reliability was tested using Construct Reliability (CR), with $CR > 0.70$ indicating acceptable reliability (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017).

Normality testing was conducted to confirm that the data satisfied the assumption of normal distribution. This was assessed using histogram curves, normal probability plots, and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test.

Data analysis comprised descriptive and verificative techniques. Descriptive analysis summarized questionnaire responses based on score ranges (Sudjana & Ibrahim, 2012). Verificative analysis employed Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using Lisrel 8.8 software, chosen for its ability to handle latent variables and correct measurement errors in dependent and independent variables (Efferin et al., 2008). Model fit was evaluated using established goodness-of-fit indicators (Wirasmita, 2008).

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RESULTS

The descriptive analysis of respondent characteristics revealed that the majority of participating faculty members were women, reflecting recruitment trends in health education institutions. In terms of age, most respondents were within the ranges of 46–55 years and above 55 years, indicating long-standing service and highlighting the challenge of faculty regeneration. With respect to educational attainment, the majority of respondents held a Master’s degree, while the proportion of those with a Doctoral degree remained limited, suggesting low motivation or limited opportunities to pursue higher-level education. Based on tenure, most faculty members had worked for more than 20 years, further reinforcing the indication of suboptimal regeneration of teaching staff. Regarding academic positions, the majority of respondents were at the Lecturer (Lektor) level, with fewer attaining Senior Lecturer (Lektor Kepala) or Professor (Guru Besar). This finding reflects obstacles in academic rank progression, particularly those associated with the requirements for scientific publication.

Instrument validity and reliability were assessed prior to data analysis. Validity testing confirmed that all research variables—including competence, remuneration, information technology facilities, career development, work ethic, and faculty performance—had calculated *r* values greater than the critical value of 0.300, thereby meeting the validity criteria. Reliability testing further indicated that all variables achieved coefficients above 0.700, affirming the consistency of the measurement instrument. Normality testing using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk methods showed that the data were normally distributed, with *p*-values greater than 0.05.

The descriptive analysis of each research variable is summarized as follows: 1) Faculty Competence – This variable comprised four dimensions and 17 indicators, yielding a mean score of 3.543 with a standard deviation of 0.342. The score range of 3.201 to 3.885 indicates that faculty competence was generally in the “fair” to “good” categories. The lowest-scoring indicator was the dissemination of research innovations in the form of technology and publications. 2) Remuneration – Consisting of five dimensions and 16 indicators, this variable recorded a mean score of 3.504 and a standard deviation of 0.238. The score range of 3.264 to 3.734 placed it in the “fair” to “good” categories. Particular attention was required regarding the equity of remuneration compared to other higher education institutions. Overall, all dimensions were categorized as “fairly high” to “high.” 3) Information Technology Facilities – This variable included three dimensions and 15 indicators, with a mean score of 3.414 and a standard deviation of 0.388. The score range of 3.026 to 3.801 indicated categories from “fairly complete” to “complete.” Indicators requiring improvement included the utilization of e-learning platforms, e-books, and online literature access. The recapitulation across dimensions showed that all aspects remained within the “fairly complete” to “complete” categories. 4) Career Development – Comprising five dimensions and 20 indicators, this variable achieved a mean score of 3.374 with a standard deviation of 0.213. The score range of 3.238 to 3.660 placed it within the “fair” to “good” categories. Indicators requiring more attention included staff reassignment to fill vacant positions and the implementation of education-related regulations, particularly those concerning career advancement. Overall, career development was assessed as “fair” to “good.” 5) Work Ethic – This variable contained three dimensions and 19 indicators, with a mean score of 3.463 and a standard deviation of 0.174. The score range of 3.288 to 3.637 placed it in the “fair” to “good” categories. Indicators requiring attention included the ability to complete tasks flexibly with minimal time and cost, and efforts to avoid unnecessary delays or waste. The overall recapitulation confirmed that work ethic fell within the “fair” to “good” categories. 6) Faculty Performance – This variable consisted of four dimensions and 20 indicators, yielding a mean score of 3.431 with a standard deviation of 0.412. The score range of 3.019 to 3.843 indicated categories of “fair” to “good.” Aspects requiring greater attention included research publications in international journals and the development of research outputs into appropriate technologies and academic books. Recapitulation across dimensions showed that faculty performance overall remained in the “fair” to “good” categories.

Table 1. Recapitulation of the Magnitude of Each Variable’s Influence

Variable	Direct Influence	Indirect Influence				Total PTL	Total Influence
		X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄		
Competence X ₁	17.10%		3.30%	1.20%	1.50%	6.00%	23.10%
Remuneration X ₂	17.70%	3.30%		1.00%	1.80%	6.10%	23.90%
IT Facility X ₃	5.30%	1.20%	1.00%		2.20%	4.40%	9.70%
Career Development X ₄	11.20%	1.50%	1.80%	2.20%		5.50%	16.70%
Total Influence of X towards Y							73.40%

Source: Results of manual data processing using Microsoft Excel 2025

The results of the verification analysis presented in Table 1 indicate that each variable contributes differently to lecturers’ work ethic. Lecturer competence exerts a direct influence of 17.1% and a total influence (direct and indirect) of 23.1%, making it the

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second most influential factor in shaping work ethic. This finding underscores that the higher the competence of lecturers, the stronger their work ethic tends to be. Lecturer remuneration emerges as the most dominant variable in shaping work ethic, with a direct effect of 17.7% and a total effect of 23.9%. These results suggest that adequate remuneration plays a crucial role in enhancing lecturers' motivation and dedication in fulfilling their professional responsibilities.

Meanwhile, information technology facilities demonstrate the lowest direct influence among the variables, at 5.3%, with a total influence of 9.7%. Although information technology facilities can support performance and productivity, their effect on work ethic remains relatively limited compared to other variables. Career development also contributes to shaping work ethic, with a direct effect of 11.2% and a total effect of 16.7%. While its influence is lower than that of competence and remuneration, career development remains an important aspect to consider in strengthening lecturers' professionalism.

In terms of model fit, the results of the goodness-of-fit test demonstrate that the estimated model meets the criteria based on RMSEA and SRMR (< 0.08), as well as NFI, TLI, CFI, RFI, and IFI (> 0.80). Thus, it can be concluded that the model estimation is acceptable, indicating that the empirical model obtained is consistent with the theoretical model.

Table 2. Summary of Simultaneous Test Results

R Square	Fvalue	Ftable	Conclusion
0,734	148,32	2,414	Rejected Ho

The simultaneous test was conducted to determine whether lecturer competence, remuneration, information technology facilities, and career development collectively influence lecturers' work ethic. The summary of the simultaneous testing presented in Table 2 shows that the calculated F-value of 148.32 is greater than the critical F-table value of 2.414 at a 5% significance level. Accordingly, the null hypothesis (H_0), which states that there is no significant simultaneous effect, is rejected. This finding indicates that the four variables jointly exert a significant influence on the work ethic of lecturers at Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y. These results highlight that improving lecturers' work ethic requires a comprehensive approach, encompassing the enhancement of competence, the provision of fair remuneration, the availability of adequate information technology facilities, and continuous support for career development.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of data analysis, lecturer competence at Poltekkes X and Y was categorized as fairly good to good, with personality emerging as the highest dimension. This is reflected in the lecturers' noble character and role-model behavior. However, improvement is still required in information technology skills and publication capabilities. To enhance professional competence, training, increased digital literacy, and strengthening networks with academic communities and industry are necessary.

Lecturer remuneration was also categorized as fairly high to high, with fairness identified as the dimension requiring greater attention. Remuneration improvement can be achieved through workload analysis, adjustment to economic indicators, and active involvement of lecturers in policy evaluation.

Furthermore, information technology facilities were categorized as fairly complete to complete, with user satisfaction as the highest dimension. Nevertheless, user satisfaction regarding the Learning Management System (LMS) still requires attention. Thus, a needs assessment, training, and optimization of the LMS are recommended.

Career development for lecturers was also categorized as fairly good to good, with years of service as the strongest dimension due to the experience accumulated by lecturers. Conversely, staff rotation requires attention, given concerns regarding transparency and fairness. Competency-based rotation policies, coupled with lecturer involvement in the process, are therefore needed.

Lecturers' work ethic was also categorized as fairly good to good, with interpersonal skills emerging as the strongest dimension, as reflected in effective communication and problem-solving abilities. However, reliability remains a concern, as stronger commitment is needed to complete tasks, particularly publications. This can be improved through performance management, enhanced communication, and incentive systems.

Finally, lecturer performance was assessed as fairly good to good, with international journal publication identified as the dimension that still requires significant improvement. This can be addressed through scientific writing training, coaching clinics, and expanding collaborative networks to secure research grants.

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Lecturer competence had the second-largest influence on work ethic, amounting to 23.1%, whereas information technology facilities had the smallest effect, at 9.7%. Overall, competence, remuneration, information technology facilities, and career development exerted a positive influence on work ethic, with a total contribution of 73.4%. This indicates that improvements in these variables will enhance work ethic in accordance with their respective path coefficients.

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The Influence of Competence on the Work Ethic of Lecturers at Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y

Lecturer competence had the second-largest influence on work ethic, with a direct effect of 17.1% and a total effect of 23.1%. Competence plays a crucial role in shaping work ethic as it encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that support lecturers in carrying out teaching, research, and community service (Spencer & Spencer, 1993). Lecturers with high levels of competence tend to possess greater self-confidence and motivation, consistent with Weber's theory of work ethic and Bandura's self-efficacy theory, which emphasize that belief in one's abilities influences motivation and performance (Bandura, 1997). These findings align with the studies of Ardiansyah and Putra & Rahman, which demonstrated that enhancing lecturer competence through professional development contributes to the improvement of work ethic and teaching quality (Ardiansyah, 2021; Putra & Rahman, 2020). Strengthening professional competence should therefore be supported through research and publication incentives, access to resources, as well as training in research methodology and academic writing. Furthermore, curriculum evaluation and updates, along with the application of innovative teaching methods, are necessary to ensure that lecturers are more confident and competent in fulfilling their responsibilities.

The Effect of Remuneration on Work Ethic among Lecturers at Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y

Remuneration exerts the most dominant influence on lecturers' work ethic, with a direct effect of 17.7% and a total effect of 23.9%. Among its dimensions, fairness demonstrates the strongest reflection of remuneration, while transparency appears to be the weakest. Adequate remuneration enhances motivation, job satisfaction, and lecturers' dedication, creating a positive cycle in which appropriate compensation fosters stronger work ethics. When lecturers perceive their compensation as fair and commensurate with their contributions, they are more motivated to perform at their best.

Siregar's research indicates that remuneration affects work ethic through motivation and job satisfaction (Fauzi & Siregar, 2019). Nahar and Zayed emphasize that salary and incentives function as motivational tools that drive employees' work spirit (Nahar & Zayed, 2019). Similarly, Davidescu et al. found that financial remuneration constitutes a crucial factor in shaping employees' work ethic (Davidescu et al., 2020). The findings of this study suggest that adequate remuneration not only strengthens individual lecturers' work ethic but also enhances the institutional competitiveness in attracting highly qualified teaching staff. Improving the remuneration system for lecturers through salary structure evaluation, workload analysis, and adjustments aligned with inflation and living costs will foster a more conducive work environment, enabling lecturers to contribute and innovate without being burdened by financial constraints.

The Influence of Information Technology Facilities on the Work Ethic of Lecturers at Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y

Information Technology (IT) facilities influence lecturers' work ethic, although the effect is relatively smaller compared to other variables, with a direct effect of 5.34% and a total effect of 10.52%. The relatively low impact of IT facilities may be attributed to their role as supporting tools rather than the primary determinants of work ethic, as well as the varying levels of utilization among lecturers. According to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), technology adoption is influenced by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Davis, 1989). If IT facilities enhance productivity, lecturers are more likely to be motivated. However, the extent of this impact still depends on the degree of technology integration within the work environment (Ojeleye, 2017). The DeLone and McLean Information System Success Model also highlights that system quality and user satisfaction determine the effectiveness of IT facilities in improving work ethic (DeLone & McLean, 2003). Proper management of IT facilities can enhance lecturers' work efficiency, access to educational resources, as well as academic collaboration and communication. Optimally utilized IT facilities support the teaching-learning process, facilitate access to scientific journals, and improve administrative efficiency, thereby indirectly contributing to the enhancement of lecturers' work ethic.

The Influence of Career Development on the Work Ethic of Lecturers at Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y

Career development contributes to lecturers' work ethic, with a direct effect of 11.2% and a total effect of 16.7%, although this influence remains lower than that of competence and remuneration. While career development plays an important role in enhancing motivation and job satisfaction, its impact on work ethic is comparatively smaller than that of competence and remuneration. Career development—which includes training, certification, and promotion—functions primarily as a long-term motivator, whereas competence and remuneration have a more immediate effect on productivity and work motivation. Consequently, career development should be balanced with improvements in competence and remuneration to foster a productive academic environment.

According to Expectancy Theory, lecturers are more motivated when they perceive clear career development opportunities (Vroom, 1964). Social Exchange Theory similarly emphasizes that institutional support in career development can enhance work ethic as a form of reciprocal commitment (Blau, 1964). Studies by Wahyuni et al. and Firmansyah ED et al. indicate that career development can enhance lecturers' intrinsic motivation, but its effectiveness is maximized when supported by improvements in remuneration and competence (Wahyuni et al., 2025; Firmansyah et al., 2024). Therefore, strategies aimed at improving work ethic should incorporate a balanced combination of short-term and long-term incentives.

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The Influence of Work Ethic on Lecturer Performance at Poltekkes X and Poltekkes Y

The total effect of work ethic on lecturer performance reached 81.3%, highlighting the critical importance of enhancing work ethic through competence, remuneration, technology, and career development. A high work ethic significantly impacts the quality and productivity of lecturers in teaching, research, and community service. Max Weber's theory emphasizes that work ethic represents a moral obligation that drives discipline and responsibility (Ridwan, 2006), while McClelland's motivation theory suggests that the need for achievement plays a role in enhancing performance (McClelland, 1961).

Studies by Saleha and Prasetyo & Wahyuddin support a positive relationship between work ethic and performance (Saleha, 2016; Prasetyo & Wahyuddin, 2003), while Yousef asserts that organizational commitment, as an expression of work ethic, can improve overall institutional performance (Yousef, 2000). Lecturers with a high work ethic serve as role models, fostering a culture of academic excellence and enhancing the reputation and quality of education.

Strategies to strengthen work ethic include soft skills training, cultivating a positive work environment, and providing recognition for high-performing lecturers. Policies that support well-being, flexibility, and professional development are also necessary. The findings of this study can inform institutional management in designing more effective policies, while further research is warranted to explore additional factors, such as organizational culture and leadership.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that lecturer competence, remuneration, information technology facilities, and career development at Poltekkes X and Y are generally adequate, though improvements are required in professionalism, remuneration fairness, IT user satisfaction, and promotion policies. Lecturer work ethic, while moderate to good, needs reinforcement in persistence and commitment, and performance remains limited, particularly in research and publication.

Competence, remuneration, IT facilities, and career development positively influence work ethic (73.4%), with remuneration and competence as dominant factors. Work ethic significantly enhances lecturer performance (81.3%). Strengthening competence, financial welfare, technological infrastructure, and career development is therefore crucial to improving overall lecturer performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the data analysis, enhancing faculty competence, remuneration, information technology facilities, and career development at Poltekkes X and Y requires a more strategic approach. Faculty competence should be strengthened through continuous training, access to scientific forums, and research-teaching collaboration. Transparent remuneration policies, performance-based incentives, and benchmarking with peer institutions are essential to improve satisfaction with the salary system. Information technology facilities need improvement through user satisfaction surveys, stronger infrastructure, and training for academic use. Career development should be supported by fair transfer policies, leadership programs, and regular evaluation of promotion systems.

Moreover, a strong faculty work ethic is vital for improving academic performance, with reliability, self-confidence, intrinsic motivation, and work-life balance as key factors. Institutions should foster a positive work culture through clear performance management, effective communication, and recognition of faculty dedication. Strengthening the work ethic is expected to significantly enhance faculty performance in research, teaching, and community service, thereby improving institutional reputation and graduate quality.

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